

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3240-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 132 - Part 3

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18459>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 108 and 132. for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different** orders — specifically orders 3, 4,5,6,7,8, 18 and 12 — each contributing a distinct structural layer.*

*The innermost core is a magic square of order 12 formed by different-sum magic squares of order 3. Successive borders of orders 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 18 and 12 are then applied; **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In case of order 8, first three are of equal-sums and last three are of different sums. The same is with order 18, i.e., not all are with equal magic sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations:*

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, pandiagonal magic squares, block-wise construction, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [?, ?, ?, ?, ?, ?, ?] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [?, ?, ?, ?, ?, ?] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [?, ?, ?]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [?, ?, ?, ?]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [?, ?, ?, ?, ?]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [?].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [?] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [?, ?, ?, ?, ?, ?].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [?, ?, ?].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [?].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [?].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [?].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [?].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [?].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [?].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [?].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [?].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [?].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [?, ?, ?, ?, ?, ?, ?].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [?, ?].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [?, ?].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [?, ?].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [?, ?].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [?, ?].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [?].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [?].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [?].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [?].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 108 and 132. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

• **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

• **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

(b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

• **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

(c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

• **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

(a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

• **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

(b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

(c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

• **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

(b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.

(c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.

(e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.

(f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

• **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 18**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.

(a) The first is composed of two types of 6 magic squares of order 6. One is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. The second type is a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and a **pandigonal** magic square of order 4 in the upper-left corner. These are considered in four corners with four different directions resulting a beautiful symmetric magic square of order 18.

(b) The second is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 18 embedded with four equal sums magic squares of order 8 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle of all four.

(c) The third is **cyclic-type** magic square of order 18 composed of four equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 embedded with a **single-layer bordered** magic squares of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle,

(d) The forth is **triple-layer bordered** magic square of order 18. The external boarder is composed of different sums magic squares of order 3. The internal part is a magic square of order 12 composed of two equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×12 .

- (e) The fifth is a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×8 and two equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 .
- (f) The sixth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic squares of order 18 **bordered** with four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. It is composed four equal sums **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×10 embedded with **single-layer** magic square of order 6 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.
- **7th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 12**
 1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 12.
 - (a) The first is composed of four equal sums **cornered** magic squares of order 6, where there are 8 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 4 equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 - (b) The second is also composed of four equal sums **cornered** magic squares of order 6 in different positions, where there are 8 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 4 equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 - (c) The third composed of 2 **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×8 . The internal and external parts are 12 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 .
 - (d) The forth is composed of 6 **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 embedeed with equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
 - (e) The fifth is also composed of 6 equal sums **plain magic rectangles** of order 4×6 .
 - (f) The sixth is a **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 10×12 covered by two single rows of order 1×12 forming a magic square of order 12.

Below summarises the six construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**
 - Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.
- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**
 - In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**
 - In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

- In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 18**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 72 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 108.
- **7th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 12**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 12. Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 108 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 132.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord.90}} = 1(3) \times 2(4) \times 3(5) \times 3(6) \times 5(7) \times 6(8) \times 6(18) \times 6(12) = 19940. \quad (2)$$

More details of last border i.e., 7th border of magic squares of order 112 are given in the following section.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 132

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 132, we applied following six different types of magic squares of order 12 over the magic squares of order 108:

12	mgc												870	12	mgc												870		
		137	8	17	130	11	132	24	122	120	126	21	22	870			17	130	11	132	137	8	119	26	35	112	29	114	870
		143	2	12	131	18	129	23	121	25	19	124	123	870			12	131	18	129	135	10	125	20	30	113	36	111	870
		135	10	134	13	128	15	27	118	35	112	29	114	870			134	13	128	15	143	2	117	28	116	31	110	33	870
		9	136	127	16	133	14	125	20	30	113	36	111	870			127	16	133	14	9	136	27	118	109	34	115	32	870
		6	140	138	144	4	3	117	28	116	31	110	33	870			4	3	144	138	6	140	24	122	120	126	22	21	870
		5	139	7	1	141	142	119	26	109	34	115	32	870			141	142	1	7	5	139	23	121	25	19	123	124	870
		71	76	65	78	83	62	39	40	108	102	42	104	870			57	58	90	84	60	86	42	104	102	108	39	40	870
		66	77	72	75	81	64	106	105	37	43	41	103	870			88	87	55	61	59	85	41	103	43	37	106	105	870
		80	67	74	69	89	56	53	94	47	96	45	100	870			71	76	65	78	63	82	45	100	53	94	47	96	870
		73	70	79	68	63	82	48	95	54	93	99	46	870			66	77	72	75	81	64	107	38	48	95	54	93	870
		58	57	90	84	60	86	98	49	92	51	107	38	870			80	67	74	69	89	56	99	46	98	49	92	51	870
		87	88	55	61	59	85	91	52	97	50	101	44	870			73	70	79	68	83	62	101	44	91	52	97	50	870
1		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	2		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

12	mgc												870	12	mgc												870		
		12	141	2	139	1	135	142	8	49	95	94	52	870			116	30	117	32	26	114	43	103	107	101	40	41	870
		138	126	19	122	23	13	132	7	96	50	51	93	870			118	110	36	111	33	27	106	99	98	48	45	39	870
		5	20	125	123	22	131	14	140	57	87	86	60	870			25	35	109	34	112	120	37	46	47	97	100	108	870
		134	127	18	24	121	130	15	11	88	58	59	85	870			31	115	28	113	119	29	104	42	38	44	105	102	870
		9	17	128	21	124	16	129	136	53	91	90	56	870			138	6	141	2	8	140	128	18	129	20	14	126	870
		137	4	143	6	144	10	3	133	92	54	55	89	870			144	12	9	135	134	1	130	24	21	123	122	15	870
		65	79	78	68	109	27	119	30	120	28	34	113	870			3	133	136	10	11	142	13	121	124	22	23	132	870
		80	66	67	77	116	37	108	45	100	41	104	29	870			5	139	4	143	137	7	19	127	16	125	131	17	870
		69	75	74	72	35	107	38	99	46	103	42	110	870			90	56	93	54	50	92	80	66	62	81	68	78	870
		76	70	71	73	31	106	39	98	47	102	43	114	870			51	87	57	86	60	94	82	72	69	75	74	63	870
		61	83	82	64	112	40	105	48	97	44	101	33	870			96	58	88	59	85	49	61	73	76	70	71	84	870
		84	62	63	81	32	118	26	115	25	117	111	36	870			53	89	52	91	95	55	67	79	83	64	77	65	870
3		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	4		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

12	mgc												870	12	mgc												870
	1	140	3	4	143	144	48	38	39	106	107	97	870		61	72	83	64	65	79	78	68	69	75	74	82	870
	139	2	141	142	5	6	102	101	100	45	44	43	870		8	135	6	129	2	140	128	11	132	20	18	141	870
	138	137	136	9	8	7	103	104	105	40	41	42	870		7	120	36	114	118	111	115	35	22	21	33	138	870
	12	11	10	135	134	133	37	47	46	99	98	108	870		136	122	48	40	108	100	39	43	103	99	23	9	870
	25	26	27	118	119	120	13	14	15	130	131	132	870		15	116	104	91	51	53	55	96	89	41	29	130	870
	115	116	117	28	29	30	127	128	129	16	17	18	870		142	24	38	50	58	85	88	59	95	107	121	3	870
	114	113	112	33	32	31	126	125	124	21	20	19	870		126	26	98	93	87	60	57	86	52	47	119	19	870
	36	35	34	111	110	109	24	23	22	123	122	121	870		12	32	101	56	94	92	90	49	54	44	113	133	870
	49	50	51	94	95	96	61	62	81	64	83	84	870		131	28	46	105	37	45	106	102	42	97	117	14	870
	91	92	88	57	53	54	79	80	63	82	65	66	870		144	112	109	31	27	34	30	110	123	124	25	1	870
	60	89	93	52	56	85	72	77	76	69	68	73	870		4	10	139	16	143	5	17	134	13	125	127	137	870
	90	59	58	87	86	55	78	71	70	75	74	67	870		84	73	62	81	80	66	67	77	76	70	71	63	870
4	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	4	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.
 1. The first is composed of four equal sums **cornered** magic squares of order 6, where there are 8 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 4 equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 2. The second is also composed of four equal sums **cornered** magic squares of order 6 in different positions, where there are 8 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 4 equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 3. The third composed of 2 **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 6×8 . The internal and external parts are 12 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 .
 4. The forth is composed of 6 **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 embedeed with equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
 5. The fifth is also composed of 6 equal sums **plain magic rectangles** of order 4×6 .
 6. The sixth is a **single-layer bordered magic rectangles** of order 10×12 covered by two single rows of order 1×12 forming a magic square of order 12.

Combing 3240 magic squares of order 108 and 6 magic squares of order 12 lead us to 19940 different types of magic squares of order 132. Since this number is too high, so we worked with only 3240 magic squares of order 132. See below few examples in figures:

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3240 magic squares of order 132 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 18 and 12. More details are in an **excel file** attached with the work.

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